

DESCRIPTION OF THE USED ALGORITHM FOR AUTOMATION OF QUALITY CONTROL TEXTILE MATERIALS

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Abstract: The purpose of this thesis is to automate the online detection of weaving defects by a computerized system based on image processing software. Obviously, fabric inspection has an importance to prevent the risk of delivering inferior quality product. Until recently, the visual defect detection is still undertaken offline and manually by humans with many drawbacks such as tiredness, boredom and, inattentiveness. Usually, after the produced fabric is doffed from the weaving machines, it is batched into large rolls and sent to the inspection department. A skilled staff rolls the fabric at high speed on the inspection machine under sufficient light to identify all defects. Besides the mentioned drawbacks, the lag time exists between defect creation and detection causes more second choice fabric. Fortunately, the continuous development in computer technology introduces the online automated fabric inspection as an effective alternative.

Key words: automate, inspection machine, important, computer vision system, management activities, products, development.

The explained basic algorithms and technique require robust strategy to be implemented. Figure (4.35) presents the flow-chart of this strategy along with the different steps. Such strategy revolves around the detection principle that describes textures in fabric images by a series of features derived from their fast Fourier transform at different levels of resolution. The defect-free image contains only one texture. It means that its all defect-free sub-images will contain the same important or significant information as the original image. Otherwise, the sub-image has a defect.

The input images are first cropped into many sub-images. Each of these images is Fourier-transformed and then a set of local statistical measures (features) is computed as local energies (peak values) which represents the first step. These values correspond to the power contained in a certain frequency range in the image.

The previous procedure is implemented firstly on the simulated fabric images to determine and optimize the most important detection parameters.

Then, it is implemented on different images of real fabric which contain the same pre-determined defects of simulated images. The object here is to prove the utility of the technique to detect defects in case of a real fabric and in case of a simulated one.

To improve the credibility of the technique and overcome the problem of detection errors, a second step is implemented using a level selection filter. Through this filter, the technique is able to detect only the actual or real defects and highlight its exact dimensions.

In all previous steps all used images have pre-determined defects. We need to obtain unsupervised defect detection in which any defect should be highlighted regardless it is considered in the training stage or not. Therefore, several images containing some random defects will be used to confirm the ability of the technique in the unsupervised conditions.

The last step is to examine the technique during the weaving process *i.e.* in real conditions. In addition, the detection results could be used to develop daily reports of defective products or any other quality reports. Also, we can mark the selvedge of fabric roll at a place parallel to the existed defect as usual.

This strategy is summarized in the next flow-chart whereas some steps have to be introduced with more details to describe how it actually takes place. The next part of the chapter addresses these steps besides any other important information not mentioned in the strategy.

The implementation of this algorithm takes place through the technique of cross-correlation, *i.e.* linear operations. They examine the structure regularity features of the fabric image in the Fourier domain using a random sub-image scans the main fabric image. To ensure the success of the technique,

following rational steps are considered:

1. We developed a fabric defect map. From this map, twelve defect types are determined as the major defects which should be considered during the pre- processing step.

2. We developed simulated plain fabric images either free of defects or containing these twelve defect types. The objective of this step is to understand the behaviour of the technique and to determine and then optimize the most important factors or parameters which affect on the process.

3. To verify the success of the technique in reality, it is then implemented on real fabricimages containing the same defects types as in case of simulated images.

This thesis illustrated an effective automated fabric inspection technique which was applied on plain fabric through various procedures. Meanwhile, there are some essential aspects where the method's performance can be enhanced. We therefore propose the next points as possible outlines for further work.

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